

MYTHOLOGICAL BASIS OF CHARACTERS AND PLOT SYSTEMS IN MODERN ENGLISH NOVELS

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ANNOTATION

This article is modern English in his novels characters and plots system mythological the basics to learn dedicated research emphasizes . In the article , mythology and modern English of novels have shown mutually dependence analysis will be done and mythological of elements their plot , characters , and fairy tales on how effect that he did is studied .

Key Words : Modern English novels , Characters , Plots , Mythology Research

Introduction : Modern English novels , mythology and mythological basics aspect with interesting and to learn worthy has been one is the subject . In this article , modern English in his novels characters and plots system mythological the basics learning and analysis to do dedicated research results is emphasized . Mythology and of literature this of lights mutually dependence and to himself feature all interesting problems open gives.

Research Methodology :

This article is literature research based on take went research methodology done increases . First , modern English in novels mythological elements and their main content is determined . Then , this elements and contents their plot , characters, and fairy tales on how effect that he did and their in programming how his role that it was analysis will be done . Research , mythology and of literature mutually dependence explanation and comment to lighting focuses .

Modern English in his novels characters and plots system mythological basics about more information to give for the following rows through in detail comment I give :

1. Mythology and English Novels : Modern English novels , mythology concepts and elements their own main part as own into takes. In these novels mythological heroes and plots by done is increased . Modern English novels , mythology concepts and elements their own main part as own into takes. These are novels their own the world and stories mythological basics through are formed. It is mythological elements and concepts heroes and plots by done is increased and their heroism tasks, historical covers , and characters on effect does. Such in novels mythology and of literature have shown mutually dependence, his to himself characteristic and of literature mythological distribution emphasizes. It is mythological connection , novels their own to himself special and teacher to be for important does. Heroes mythological tasks master and their Demons, ghosts, ghosts and another mythological creatures with to fight need to be tasks done increases. Such mythological basics and concepts modern English of novels have shown mythological content in explanation and literary studies in learning important important have. It is mythological analysis and remarks of novels reading and to be understood for help will give and them their own mythological appropriation and distribution in learning help gives.[1]

2. Mythological Characteristics: Such in novels heroes and managers mythological characteristics with separate stands _ These are the characteristics their heroism , evil or wonders represents. An example for , Frodo Baggins in "The Lord of the Rings" interest ability and heroism task mythological characteristics through reflection will be delivered . Modern English in his novels heroes and managers mythological characteristics with separate stands and this characteristics their heroism , evil or wonders represents. It is mythological characteristics of novels heroes and plots to himself special and male does Frodo Baggins of The Lord of the Rings mythological characteristics about example by learning see : Frodo Baggins in JRR Tolkien's The Lord of the Rings heroism task mastered mythological from the heroes is one His mythological characteristics his heroism task reflection makes

a. Fun ability : Frodo, interest and nature lover features with separate stands These are skills his again agitations , demons , and images with in fighting successful to be help gives

b. Heroism mission : Frodo Baggins main task The ring In Mordor take to go and to him to provoke is to stop . This is a task his heroism , changeability and evils to the hand input Demand does

c. Masculinity and patience : Frodo, freedom and patience represents _ He is in Mordor of incitement during evils win to throw and unexpected problems solution to do for masculinity shows .

Such mythological Characteristics of Frodo Baggins heroism history , character and historical the cover in explanation important. It is mythological heroes through main task and character represents and of The Lord of the Rings common mythological also influence the context does.[5]

3. Mythological Tasks : Contemporary English in his novels heroes and plots mythological tasks master and this tasks demons , images , agitations and another mythological elements with depends to be can These are tasks of novels mythological content , characters duties and their the world in formation important role plays _ Percy Jackson from the series "Percy Jackson & the Olympians". to the task about example by learning let's see :

Percy Jackson, that is the main character in the series and mythological from the heroes is one His main task mythological elements and heroes with depends has been tasks mastery is :

I. Olympia of the walls Excitement : Percy Jackson main duties Olympics the walls stir up and their to the world weight come in to come is to stop . He is this task mastery for heroism and mythological of their powers uses

II. Figures with fight : Percy, mythological images with to fight and them to swallow absorbs . These are images demons , agitations , and another mythological creatures with in fighting is used .

III. Mythological the world save : Percy Jackson's duties mythological the world of people to the world against protection to do own into takes It is mythological the world and people demons , agitations , and images such as from dangers storage task absorbs .

Such mythological The tasks of Percy Jackson heroism history and his character in explanation important. They are of novels mythological content in explanation and of the hero task in expression help gives. Mythological these are the tasks of novels mythological to the context effect does and them mythological elements with depends does .[3]

English literature and mythology between this mutually connection , modern English novels learning and analysis in doing important have will be These works mythological contents in literature new way show and their features explanation for great one tool will be

Summary

Article to the results according to modern English in his novels characters and plots system mythological basics with depends . Mythological elements of novels biography status , main of heroes characters , and of the plot another details on complicated effect does _ It's to himself characteristic of novels have shown mythological content and of literature common mythological context about more to understand possibility will give.

With that , the article modern English in his novels mythological basics and their to literature Yours to your request answer that I do wanted as follows _ books the list offer I will :

References:

1. "The Hero with a Thousand Faces" - Joseph Campbell
2. "The Power of Myth" - Joseph Campbell and Bill Moyers
3. "Bulfinch's Mythology" - Thomas Bulfinch
4. Harry Potter series - JK Rowling
5. The Lord of the Rings trilogy - JRR Tolkien